

CORRUPTION IS THE DECOMPOSITION OF CIVIL SOCIETY

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ABSTRACT

This article provides data on corruption. The measures implemented against corruption in Uzbekistan and the laws adopted are described. The paper starts with a short review of the basic definitions of corruption, and then moves on to an overview of factors contributing to or constraining corruption, together with a brief overview of the relevant patterns. The article concludes with suggestions for forthcoming research, as well as a brief description of the information sources and key variables used in this study.

Keywords: Corruption, Experience, Uzbekistan, History, Law, World, terriblest sickness, civil society

INTRODUCTION

It is known that as communities evolve, so do the laws. Every country develops its own law. The most unfortunate thing is that some people, when they break the law, they attempt to justify themselves by stating that they will be released. They tend to try to exonerate themselves by telling them that they will be let off. For instance, a law-breaker he also breaks another law by offering a bribe to a defender of the law. In this article we want to talk about bribery, that is, "corruption!" he is caught breaking the law and being punished, but he escapes that punishment he also breaks another law by offering a bribe to a defender of the law¹. In this article we want to talk about bribery, that is, "corruption!" Corruption is the "worm" that is devouring the "tree" of civil society. When it comes to corruption, it torments society in various ways

it is a terriblest sickness. The corruption impedes the rise of the country, the democracy prevents its development. As a consequence, the people are lagging behind. Their sense of human reason arises a mood of indifference and indifference. The people see that their freedoms, rights and duties are being violated, stands and treats it with indifference. As a result, it has no effect on the environment. Bribery is identified in the Qur'an: "Do not consume one another's possessions in vain. "Do not waste your wealth, which you know, on behalf of the people as for sin" (Surah al-Baqarah, 188).²The most widespread types of corruption are those of bribery, dishonesty, extortion, and nepotism. Since the struggle for independence, a number of legal regulations have

been adopted to combat crime, and although government agencies and their structures have been established to deal with it, the fight against corruption is going on as usual. Corruption crime has literally set down roots and its number is increasing day by day. The most dangerous is people's indifference to this situation, to treat it as a normal situation. If we look more deeply, corruption is an economic crime associated with it. In the current economic and political situation, agriculture is the main source of development, which belongs to the state and provides it. Corruption is one of the most significant issues that must be dealt with on a global scale. Therefore, the battle against it has raised to the global level and has become one of the important problems of world policy. That is why, everyone knows that this vice is not only a serious obstacle on the way of reforms, but also a straightforward danger to achieving the goals set during the transition period. From the very first days of independence, as part of an overall implementation strategy of developing a legal under the leadership of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Islam Karimov in a historically short period of time the country has formed a legal framework to ensure the rule of law, an effective system of countering corruption. State Program to Combat Corruption for 2019-2020 (hereafter referred to as the State Program); the Law on Counteracting Money Legalization and the Financing of Terrorism was adopted. So as to ensure the implementation of this law, the Ministry of Justice transferred a number of departmental regulatory legal documents from the state register. These include the Rules of internal control on combating legalization (laundering) of criminal incomes and terrorism financing in organizations rendering leasing services, the Rules of internal control on combating legalization (laundering) of criminal incomes and terrorism financing for organizations dealing with real estate, the Rules of internal control on combating legalization (laundering) of criminal incomes and terrorism financing. An example is the Regulation on measures and sanctions applied by the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan in relation to commercial banks, credit unions, microcredit organizations and pawnshops for violation of requirements of legal documents related to combating. In addition, the Ministry of Justice and the Prosecutor General's Office have developed a methodology for conducting an anti-corruption expert examination of draft regulatory legal documents on the basis of the requirements of the Convention.³ A number of measures have been implemented to create favorable conditions for small businesses and private entrepreneurship, remove administrative obstacles and simplify licensing and permitting procedures, improve the mechanism of public procurement, and approve rules of conduct for civil servants. Corruption and related economic crimes are a major source of danger, a security threat to development in the current economic and political situation of states. The scale of damage caused by corruption is limitless. According to the Global Financial Transparency

Organization, between 2001 and 2010, about \$6 trillion was misappropriated because of corruption in 150 developing countries around the world. China tops the list of such countries. Over the past 10 years, \$2.75 trillion has been spent on illegal transactions in that country. In Mexico, \$476 billion has now been stolen from the state treasury, which means that \$4,500 has been stolen from each citizen. The damage from corruption in Russia is \$152 billion. Nigeria is the most corrupt of African countries. Illegal capital turnover there is \$129 billion.⁴ In summary, it may be said that we must live up to the trust placed in us by our president and abide by all the laws that have been passed. It is only then that we will make our contribution to the fight against this so-called corruption! Only then will it be possible to consider that we have made a contribution to the development of our country. For this purpose, first and foremost, if we all unite and become a great force, we will be able to fight and eradicate any evil. We will never let corruption become the scourge of our future. Preventing corruption and the situations that can cause it, and in order to prevent, liberalize the economy, improve working conditions, create favorable conditions for small businesses and private entrepreneurship, remove administrative obstacles and simplify licensing and permitting procedures, the state has implemented a number of measures to improve the procurement mechanism, approval of rules of conduct of civil servants. Abu Nasr Farabiy in his work "The City of Virtuous People" noted that one of the problems hindering the building of civil society is corruption. and corruption is a cruel obstacle to the development of multilateral cooperation, business and investment. These "invisible hands" are behind the opening and closing of dozens of joint ventures every year. It seems that the true reasons for the decline of foreign investment in a country with a high level of corruption can be found in this dangerous vice.

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